

KAKAYANIN KAHIT MAHIRAP: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY OF THE LEARNING EXPERIENCES OF ALS SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS

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Kakayanin Kahit Mahirap: A Multiple Case Study of the Learning Experiences of ALS Senior High School Learners

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Abstract

The Alternative Learning System (ALS) is designed as a parallel educational pathway for individuals who did not complete their basic education through the traditional school system. This study delves into the challenges encountered by ALS students, such as limited opportunities, academic difficulties, lack of community and family support, and low self-confidence. The study also highlights the resilience and determination of ALS students in overcoming these obstacles, showcasing their efforts to earn degrees, obtain employment, and improve the lives of their families. This also emphasizes the significance of addressing the needs of ALS students through targeted interventions and support systems. It also underscores the importance of community and school collaboration in enhancing students' social awareness and intellectual capacity. Understanding the difficulties faced by ALS learners, such as financial hardships and irregular attendance, is crucial in developing coping strategies and providing the necessary resources to help them navigate their academic journey effectively. Overall, the findings emphasize the need for tailored approaches to empower ALS students and facilitate their educational advancement.

Keywords: *alternative learning system, ALS students, academic experiences, educational challenges*

Introduction

The secret to seizing innumerable opportunities and realizing one's potential is education. Tindowen et al. (2017) said that the crucial factor in the growth and advancement of a country is education. However, there are really individuals who struggle to have access to education due to many reasons. The Department of Education (DepEd) established the Alternative Learning System (ALS) as a parallel educational pathway for students who did not complete their basic education through the traditional school system. It is the best opportunity for students to continue their dreams. However, the problems of ALS students are still undoable. The participant mentioned being afraid to stand in front of other people because she felt that they thought low of her (Pascual et al., 2022).

A research was made by Lopez-Cobar (2022), Supervised Alternative Learning Programs in Southwestern Ontario, Canada. This research examines the experiences of former students who attended Alternative learning programs. This has demonstrated how these programs can lead to school truancy, dropout, and a decrease in graduation rates—this has created the negative stigma of alternative programs as “dumping grounds” for students that experience academic and behavioral difficulties in the regular system. Previous studies have described how some students in alternative education settings feel marginalized. Without any formal schooling, students could be subjected to physical and mental health stigmatization, which may lead to a lack of meaningful employment and overreliance on government assistance. According to these studies, alternative education programs appear to affecting the students’ motivation to learn.

A study conducted by Mendoza et al. (2023) in Lal-lo National High School, Lal-lo, Cagayan Valley Philippines, revealed that ALS students have numerous difficulties, including financial hardships, obligations to family, and a lack of educational resources. These findings also demonstrated the determination and resilience of ALS students, putting in much effort to earn their degrees to obtain employment and improve the lives of their families. The coping strategies could help them succeed in navigating their academic journey.

In Union National High School-Mt. Diwata Annex, where the researcher is presently connected, observes that students who enrolled in ALS lack some of the basic competencies that they are supposed to learn in their previous grade level because they did not follow the regular school. It is evident that they experienced difficulties in their academics, especially if the basic information was not learned in the previous years. As observed, common problems experienced by ALS senior learners are due to lack of family support and being over-aged. It also includes their domestic responsibility, finances, and irregular attendance to school. ALS learners lack self-confidence and belief in their own abilities. Despite facing various barriers and limitations, ALS learners are resilient and determined; they are individuals who are eager to learn and improve themselves despite any challenges or obstacles in their way to pursue their academic. These learners understand the importance of continuous education and seek out opportunities to expand their knowledge and skills. Thus, I am challenged to conduct this study.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study was to explore the experiences, motivation, challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights of the six ALS Senior High School learners of UNHS-Mt. Diwata Annex for school year 2023-2024. As a guide for this endeavor, the researcher was challenged to address the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of ALS senior high school learners?

2. What is the motivation of ALS senior high school learners?
3. What are the challenges encountered by the participants in their quest for their education?
4. How do the participants cope with the challenges they encountered as ALS senior high school learners?
5. What are the insights of the participants to effectively manage their studies?

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the researcher utilized a multiple-case study approach. A case study is a methodological approach that involves an in-depth exploration of a specific bounded system, utilizing multiple forms of data collection to systematically gather information on how the system operates or functions (Mills et al., 2010). This research sought to explore the stories and experiences of six students from ALS. Thus, a multiple case study approach is suited for this research. In order to develop a better understanding of the issue, cases were carefully selected.

Participants

Purposive sampling was used for this research; the six participants were selected with the criteria that they are all ALS senior high school learners who are enrolled in Union National High School-Mt. Diwata Annex for the school year 2023-2024. The responses of the participants were gathered through IDI.

Following the process of identifying qualified research subjects, the researcher interviewed six research informants who were particularly products of ALS and were studying in UNHS-Mt. Diwata Annex, Monkayo, Davao de Oro. Participants were particularly chosen as they had personal experiences coming from the ALS community.

In addition, I identified and selected the participants using the selection criteria: they must have a different story to tell from other ALS learners.

Some experiences of these students were veterans, separated parents, breadwinners, married at a young age, prodigal, and academic failure. This made them qualify to become participants in my study.

Moreover, purposive sampling is a technique widely used in qualitative research for the identification and selection of information-rich cases for the most effective use of limited resources (Patton, 2002). This involves identifying and selecting individuals or groups who are especially knowledgeable about or experienced with a phenomenon of interest (Cresswell & Plano Clark, 2011).

Procedure

Before the study was conducted, I asked permission from the school's division superintendent for approval, and an endorsement letter was also secured from the division office of Davao De Oro. This method gave me the freedom to conduct such study in the school where I was teaching. Once the letter was approved, another letter was prepared for my principal at UNHS-Mt Diwata Annex. After everything was already settled, I immediately identified the six ALS senior high school learners using the criterion set. The ethics review committee at Assumption College of Nabunturan carefully considered the research project and determined that it falls under the exempted category, as defined by our institution's ethical guidelines.

I ensured the availability of the student participants. I asked their permission to be part of the research, informing them of the purpose of the study and supplemental awareness in my study. It was explained to the student participants that any confidential information would be treated with utmost confidentiality.

With the use of IDI, responses were gathered, recorded, transcribed, thematized, and analyzed. Before the interviews were conducted, the interview guide questions were validated by the panel of experts, who were identified by the Dean of the Graduate School.

Furthermore, the instrument was modified based on the suggestions and comments made by the validators to avoid ambiguity and linked the goals of the research and the interview questions. It was evaluated for timing and question flow, and this was done after the approval of the endorsement letters, which I submitted to the Division Office of Davao De Oro. Moreover, before the in-depth, face-to-face interviews, the participants were informed about the procedure of recording their answers through hand-written and phone recorders

Data Analysis

Data analysis in qualitative investigations would include breaking the data down into simpler forms, looking for patterns, and synthesizing the results. Consequently, thematic analysis was utilized to examine the information. To do this, a computer-based word-processing application was used to transcribe all of the audio-recorded interviews. Each transcription was coded to identify pertinent themes using the original notions from the pertinent literature as a guide and the research questions as a directive. Up to the write-up stage, the initial categories and themes were subjected to revision as they developed around the emergent codes. All the topics connected to the study were discussed and exhibited in depth through quotations that were translated from the vernacular, along with the reporting of the findings and interpretations. An expert was asked to comment on the translated quotations by contrasting them with the original

terms to make sure that all the meanings and hints were accurately captured in the translations.

Ethical Considerations

Knowing the responsibility and sensitivity of the qualitative multiple case study, the researcher adheres to the ethical considerations of this research.

According to Silverman (2007), by examining one's professional association's ethical principles, ethical considerations can be clarified. In this regard, I provided a letter of permission to the participants to allow me to conduct interviews with them. Creswell (2007) emphasized that informants should be given anonymity to protect them and that they should decide whether to divulge their personal experiences. This was the reason why I respected and observed the anonymity of the participants in order to hide their identities. The findings of the study were presented to the participants to demonstrate ethical consideration, providing them the chance to understand how crucial they are to the success of my study. The verification letter, as well as the remarks they made during the interview, were identical to the ones that were transcribed.

Accepting the assertion indicates that I recognized independent people who willingly shared knowledge. A healthy research partnership promotes openness, trust, and sensitivity to potential ethical dilemmas. Further, to ensure the observance of ethical standards, the researcher secured a letter containing the permission of the dean of the graduate school to conduct research and a letter containing the permission of the head of the institution where the research was conducted.

Results and Discussion

Research informants were chosen based on the uniqueness of their life story as a product of ALS learners in order to probe the experiences of Junior high school students of Union National High School –Mt. Diwata Annex. An in-depth interview was done during the interview with the informants. All throughout the entire interview, adherence to the informants' confidentiality of their identity and credibility was observed. Their responses were transcribed and analyzed. Themes were drawn out from their responses which paint the picture of their experiences as a student from ALS.

The sequence of the presentation for this chapter was based on the order of the research questions in the interview guide. The discussion section highlighted the themes, which were the findings in the study, and corroborated with related literature and studies.

The key participants in this study are six Senior high school students of Union National High School- Mt. Diwata Annex bearing different family life stories. Significant stories and experiences are gathered and presented in this section. The structured themes and the emerging themes were made as bases in the discussion of the findings in this study. Each theme was linked to related literature and studies to add substantially to the discussion.

Motivations to Continue Learning. This structured theme summarizes the views of six senior high school informants as to what motivates them to continue learning or studying. The emerging themes are full family support, self-pity, always dreaming about school, other people's comments, and motivation by one's own situation and one's own realization. The research informants describe their motivation to continue learning or study.

Family full support, according to Guanzon-Lapeña and Jacob (2017), examined the factors contributing to ALS learners' success in the Philippines. The study found that family support, a positive learning environment, and a learner-centered approach to teaching are essential factors contributing to ALS learners' success.

Self-pity This feeling unfolds when exploring the experiences of ALS learners regarding their social and emotional well-being. The study found that ALS learners face various social and emotional challenges, such as isolation, low self-esteem, and anxiety, which can affect their learning outcomes (Arpilleda & Cabacaba, 2018).

Always dreaming about school like what I stated in my review, related literature, according to Kołodziej (2010), highlighted the role of achievement motivation in educational aspirations and performance, suggesting that it is an important predictor of future success or failure. The informants value education and have a genuine thirst for learning. They recognize that education goes beyond acquiring a diploma or certificate, and they desire to expand their knowledge and capabilities in various subjects.

Other people's comments in the previous discussion in review-related literature prove the statement: though there were lots of challenges that hindered them from finishing the ALS sessions, their drive to change the way things were happening in their lives pushed them to strive hard for a better future. They faced a lot of sacrifices. Most people around the corners, where they came from, gave negative statements. Others tried to discourage them. Fortunately, these discouraging statements did not stop the learners from making their dreams a reality. The study by Apao et al. (2014) looked into the outcome of the program on the quality of living of ALS recipients.

Motivated by their situation in applying the self-efficacy construct to language learning contexts seems to be highly appropriate because language learners' appraisal of their ability to perform language skills affects their motivation as well as the behaviors needed to achieve a learning goal (Wu, 2006).

Realization, according to Takiko (2018), the alternative learning system is a substitute for students who are out-of-school youth, dropouts, and even adults who cannot continue their schooling, and it was implemented by the Deped. ALS offers programs focusing on assessments and tests. The students can take the accreditation and equivalency test in which when they pass it to the Deped or the government, will give them a certificate that will serve as proof that they passed the given exams. Through the ALS, they can have the chance to pursue their dreams and be employed.

Motivation to continue learning is a multifaceted phenomenon influenced by various intrinsic and extrinsic factors.

Reasons for Taking Alternative Learning System. This structured theme summarizes the experiences of six senior high school informants and their reasons for adopting an alternative learning system. The emerging themes are opportunities given by the government, multitasking, once-a-week classes, having a child to care for, and due to work and age.

Government Opportunity ALS offers a government-supported opportunity for individuals who may not have access to formal education. The Department of Education emphasizes ALS as an inclusive program (Department of Education, 2020).

Can Do Multitask The ability to Multitask ALS's flexible learning schedule enables learners to balance multiple responsibilities, such as work or family obligations (Martinez et al., 2018). ALS's flexibility helps learners integrate education with their daily lives effectively.

Once-a-week classes, according to a UNICEF (2021) study, show that many learners aspired to finish basic education and decided to enroll in the ALS program because of its flexible schedule, which enables them to attend work and/or other day-to-day commitments while studying. When they joined ALS, learners who encountered issues with lessons were less likely to complete the program.

Has a Child to Care parental responsibilities that ALS accommodates individuals with childcare responsibilities by providing a flexible learning environment (Tan et al., 2019). highlight that ALS supports parents in balancing educational pursuits with caregiving duties, thus fostering greater participation in lifelong learning.

Due to Work and Age, in fact, it is already stated in the previous review-related literature that ALS seeks to serve Filipinos regardless of their age, educational attainment, race, religion, and, most importantly, economic status. The Philippines set this program to reduce high drop-out rates among public schools and to accelerate the number of pupils/students participating in the basic education curriculum. This will help strengthen the foundations of attaining the policies and principles laid down in our constitution (Mendoza, 2015)

In conclusion, ALS not only addresses educational accessibility but also enhances flexibility and supports learners in managing diverse responsibilities. Through its inclusive approach and flexible learning options, ALS stands as a vital avenue for lifelong learning and personal development in the Philippines.

Reasons To Finish Senior High School. This structured theme summarizes the experiences of six senior high school informants as to what are the reasons for finishing senior high school. The emerging themes are finished despite people's negative comments, obtaining an education, experiencing lessons, proving something to people, having chances to work in big companies, and being able to finish despite the situation. The research informants describe their reasons for finishing senior high school. Completing senior high school represents a significant achievement with profound personal and professional benefits.

Despite people's negative comments in overcoming negative comments; many students face skepticism and negative comments about their ability to graduate. However, overcoming these challenges through determination and resilience can fuel motivation and strengthen self-confidence (Wang et al., 2012). This determination not only leads to academic success but also cultivates a mindset of perseverance in the face of adversity.

To experience lesson gaining life lessons high school education goes beyond academics, fostering crucial social and emotional skills like teamwork and time management (Eccles et al., 2011). These skills are indispensable for personal development and play a pivotal role in shaping individuals into well-rounded contributors to society.

Chances to work in big companies are enhancing employment opportunities. A high school diploma significantly broadens employment prospects and earning potential. According to the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (2019), individuals with a high school diploma experience lower unemployment rates and greater access to stable career opportunities. This credential serves as a foundation for pursuing diverse career paths and advancing in the workplace.

These qualities not only contribute to personal success but also equip individuals to handle future obstacles with confidence.

In conclusion, finishing senior high school is a transformative experience that opens doors to personal growth, enhanced opportunities, and greater resilience. From overcoming negative perceptions to gaining essential life skills and improving employability, high school completion lays a crucial foundation for lifelong success.

Experiences that Pushed to Dream. This structured theme summarized the views of six senior high school informants as to what experiences pushed them to dream. The emerging themes are hardship in life, keeping up with the new generation, and no one in the family able to finish and make children proud. The aspiration to achieve greater futures is often fueled by diverse experiences that

motivate individuals to pursue success despite challenges.

Hardship in life experiencing adversity can serve as a powerful catalyst for individuals to dream of and work towards a better future. Research by Masten et al. (2010) emphasizes that resilience in hardship fosters determination and goal-oriented behavior. Overcoming challenges cultivates a mindset focused on improvement, pushing individuals to seek opportunities for personal growth and success.

Keeping up with new generations, the rapid evolution of technology and societal norms challenges individuals to continuously adapt and learn (Prensky, 2001). discusses how the digital age necessitates ongoing skills development and education to remain competitive. This pressure to keep pace with new generations motivates individuals to set higher aspirations, driven by the desire to stay relevant and contribute meaningfully in a rapidly changing world.

Making children proud underscores how parental aspirations influence educational involvement and the transmission of values through personal achievement.

In conclusion, the drive to dream and strive for success is shaped by a variety of experiences that inspire individuals to envision better futures. Whether overcoming adversity, adapting to societal changes, breaking familial, educational cycles, or aspiring to make future generations proud, these factors underscore the transformative power of personal motivation and resilience. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for supporting individuals in realizing their aspirations and contributing positively to society's progress.

Motivations to pursue senior high school. This structured theme summarizes the views of six senior high school students as to what motivates them to pursue senior high school. The emerging themes are full family support, motivation by one's own self, difficulties in life, encouragement by loved ones, and finishing what was started. The research informants describe their motivation to pursue senior high school.

Full support from family, family support plays a crucial role in shaping students' educational journeys. According to Fan et al. (2001), parental involvement significantly enhances students' academic achievement by providing essential resources, emotional support, and encouragement. This support system helps students stay motivated and focused on their studies, ultimately contributing to their success in senior high school.

Motivated by one's own self is an intrinsic motivation that is pivotal for sustained engagement and academic success. (Deci et al. 2000) emphasize the importance of self-determination and internal satisfaction in driving students to pursue educational goals. Individuals who are intrinsically motivated set personal benchmarks and persistently strive to achieve them, thereby enhancing their educational outcomes in senior high school.

Difficulties in life, such as facing and overcoming hardships, can serve as a powerful motivator for students to pursue senior high school education (Masten, 2001). discusses resilience as a key factor, highlighting how individuals who navigate significant challenges often develop a strong determination to succeed academically. These experiences of resilience fuel their commitment to completing their education despite adversities encountered along the way.

Encouraged by loved ones, social support from peers, family members, and mentors plays a pivotal role in students' motivation to pursue educational goals note that positive reinforcement and encouragement from loved ones enhance students' academic motivation and performance. Such support systems bolster students' resolve and commitment to their senior high school education, reinforcing their sense of purpose and dedication.

Finish what was started the concept of grit, as introduced by Duckworth et al. (2007), underscores the importance of perseverance and passion in achieving long-term educational goals. Students characterized by high levels of grit are driven by a steadfast commitment to completing what they have initiated, demonstrating resilience and dedication throughout their senior high school journey.

In conclusion, the decision to pursue senior high school education is influenced by a myriad of motivational factors that encompass familial support, intrinsic motivation, resilience in adversity, encouragement from loved ones, and a strong sense of commitment to personal goals. Understanding these motivational drivers is essential for educators, policymakers, and support systems aiming to cultivate environments that foster student engagement and persistence. By nurturing these motivations, educational institutions can effectively empower students to achieve academic success and realize their full potential in senior high school and beyond.

Influence to Continue Studying. This structured theme summarizes the views of six senior high school informants as to what or who influenced them to continue studying. The emerging themes are influenced by the book of Dr. Jose Rizal, influenced by classmates, difficulties in life, faith in God, and the graduation march. This is how the research informants describe what or who influenced them to continue studying.

Influenced by the book of Dr. Jose Rizal literature, particularly the works of Dr. Jose Rizal such as "Noli Me Tangere" and "El Filibusterismo," has a profound impact on motivating individuals to continue their education. Guerrero (2010) notes that Rizal's writings advocate for the importance of education in achieving social reform and national progress, inspiring many Filipinos to value education as a tool for personal and societal advancement.

Influenced by classmates' peer influence significantly contributes to students' academic motivation and engagement. Ryan (2001)

highlights that positive relationships with classmates foster a supportive learning environment where students encourage each other to study and excel academically. Peer interactions enhance motivation and promote a sense of camaraderie, reinforcing the importance of educational pursuits.

Influenced by family support plays a pivotal role in shaping students' educational aspirations and achievements. (Hill et al. 2009) found that parental involvement positively correlates with students' academic success. The expectations, values, and encouragement provided by family members motivate students to persist in their studies and strive for educational excellence.

Difficulties in life, experiencing challenges, and adversity can serve as a powerful motivators for students to pursue education as a means of overcoming obstacles. Masten (2001) discusses resilience as a key factor, highlighting how individuals who face difficulties often develop a strong determination to succeed. These challenges instill resilience and drive students to pursue education as a pathway to a better future.

Faith in God's spiritual beliefs and faith provides students with a sense of purpose and motivation to continue their educational journey. Smith (2003) suggests that religious faith contributes to resilience and a positive outlook, helping students maintain their commitment to education despite challenges. Faith serves as a source of emotional and psychological support, reinforcing the significance of educational pursuits.

The decision to continue studying is influenced by a variety of motivational factors that encompass literary inspirations, peer interactions, familial support, resilience in adversity, spiritual beliefs, and the symbolic significance of graduation ceremonies. These influences collectively shape students' educational journeys, fostering determination, resilience, and a sense of purpose in achieving academic success. Understanding these motivational drivers is essential for educators, policymakers, and support systems to create environments that nurture and sustain student engagement and persistence in further education.

Reasons to Earn Diploma. This structured theme summarizes the views of six senior high school informants as to their reasons for earning a diploma. The emerging themes are proof/evidence of completed education, making one's own self proud, and proof of work application. This is how the research informants describe their motivation to continue learning or studying.

Proof/Evidence of Completed Education a diploma serves as concrete evidence that an individual has fulfilled the academic requirements of a specific educational program. Pascarella et al. (2005) emphasize that obtaining a diploma is crucial for demonstrating the completion of a structured educational process, which is essential for advancing to higher educational levels or for gaining credibility in professional settings. This certification validates one's educational achievements and prepares individuals for further educational opportunities.

For proof of work application in today's competitive job market, educational qualifications are often a prerequisite for employment opportunities. A diploma serves as tangible proof of an individual's knowledge, skills, and commitment to their education, making them more competitive candidates for job applications. Carnevale et al. (2010) discuss how employers view diplomas as a reliable indicator of a candidate's readiness and potential in the workforce. Beyond opening doors to job opportunities, a diploma enhances job security and increases earning potential.

The decision to earn a diploma is influenced by various compelling factors that highlight its significance in educational and professional contexts. From tangible proof of educational attainment to fostering personal pride and enhancing employability, a diploma represents a pivotal achievement in an individual's life. Understanding these reasons underscores the importance of educational milestones in shaping personal development, career opportunities, and lifelong learning. Educators, policymakers, and stakeholders play crucial roles in supporting individuals as they strive to achieve their educational goals and realize their full potential through the attainment of a diploma.

Hardest Problem Encountered That Influence to Continue Studying. Six senior high school informants from ALS share the same experiences in facing the challenges and demands of life. Out of their responses, seven themes were drawn out. These are the declaration of no man's land when applying for work, starving for 3 days, parent's separation, mining laborer, self-pity, and people's negative comments.

The Declaration of No Man's Land. Living in conflict zones or experiencing displacement disrupts education continuity, as highlighted by (UNESCO, 2011). These conditions create formidable barriers to accessing schools and maintaining regular attendance. Despite these challenges, education represents stability and empowerment, often motivating individuals to seek knowledge as a means to transcend adversity and build a better future.

Parents' separation a parental separation introduces emotional and financial instability, which can adversely affect students' academic performance. Amato (2000) discusses the negative consequences of divorce on children but also highlights resilience and support systems as crucial factors enabling students to continue their education despite familial challenges.

Self-pity is a feeling that can act as a significant psychological barrier to educational persistence. Fredrickson (2001) discusses how positive emotions and resilience play critical roles in overcoming negative feelings and empowering individuals to focus on their educational goals despite internal challenges.

In conclusion, the obstacles encountered in pursuing education are diverse and multifaceted, yet they often serve as catalysts for personal growth and resilience. From displacement and economic pressures to familial disruptions and psychological barriers, each challenge underscores the transformative power of education in overcoming adversity. Understanding these factors is essential for developing targeted interventions that support students in navigating challenges and achieving their educational aspirations.

Outcomes of Finishing Senior High School. This structured theme summarizes the views of six senior high school informants as to what the outcome of finishing senior high school will be. Out of their responses, five themes were drawn out. These are will continue to college, nothing more to worry about, able to apply for work to companies, feeling happy, and making family and others proud.

Continuation to college a primary outcome of finishing senior high school is increased access to higher education. Research indicates that high school graduates are more likely to enroll in college, which fosters intellectual development and career advancement opportunities (Baum et al., 2013). The rising college enrollment rates underscore the pivotal role of high school completion in facilitating broader educational attainment.

Nothing more to worry about is reduced stress and anxiety. Completing high school often alleviates the stress associated with academic pressures and future uncertainties. Studies show that high school graduates experience a decrease in anxiety levels post-graduation, providing a period of transition and reflection before pursuing further education or entering the workforce (Conley et al., 2013).

Able to apply work to companies' employment opportunities, high school graduation significantly enhances employability, with a diploma serving as a prerequisite for many entry-level positions. The U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (2019) highlights lower unemployment rates among high school graduates compared to those without a diploma, underscoring the diploma's importance in securing stable employment. High school education equips individuals with essential skills valued by employers, enhancing their readiness for the job market (Carnevale et al., 2012).

Feeling happy and emotional well-being after graduating from high school is associated with a sense of achievement and happiness, contributing positively to emotional well-being. Research suggests that completing high school marks a significant personal milestone, boosting self-esteem and providing clarity of purpose (Rumberger, 2011). This emotional fulfillment supports overall well-being and resilience in facing future challenges.

Making families and other people proud family pride and social recognition, the completion of high school is a source of pride for families and communities, symbolizing educational achievement and social mobility. Educational milestones, such as high school graduation, enhance social recognition and familial cohesion, reflecting broader cultural values and aspirations (Fulgini et al., 2002).

In conclusion, finishing senior high school yields diverse benefits that extend beyond academic credentials. From expanded educational opportunities and reduced stress to enhanced employability and emotional well-being, high school completion plays a pivotal role in shaping individual success and community cohesion. Understanding these outcomes underscores the significance of supporting educational attainment as a catalyst for personal fulfillment and societal advancement.

Part of Studies Finding Hard to Adjust. This structured theme summarizes the experiences of six senior high school students as to what part of the studies find hard to adjust. The emerging themes are technology, multitasking, budgeting, and carrying a child to school and work. This is how the research informants describe the challenges encountered by the participants in their quest for their education.

Technology the integration of technology in education can be daunting for adult learners who may not be as technologically adept as their younger counterparts. According to Johnson et al. (2016), many adult learners face difficulties in adapting to digital learning environments due to a lack of digital literacy and confidence. This can result in frustration and inadequacy, which may negatively impact their learning experience and academic performance. Additionally, technical issues such as software malfunctions, connectivity problems, and the complexity of new digital tools can pose significant barriers to effective learning (Brown et al., 2015). For adult learners, who may already be managing numerous responsibilities, these technological challenges can add an extra layer of difficulty to their educational pursuits.

Multitasking is a common requirement for adult learners who often juggle studies with work, family, and other commitments. Karp et al. (2008) highlight that multitasking can lead to cognitive overload and reduce academic performance. When adult learners attempt to handle multiple tasks simultaneously, their attention and cognitive resources are divided, which can diminish the quality of their work and learning outcomes. González et al. (2008) further, explain that the stress associated with balancing multiple roles can lead to burnout and decreased motivation.

Budget and financial constraints are a significant concern for adult learners. The cost of tuition, textbooks, and other educational materials can be prohibitive. Mamiseishvili et al. (2013) found that financial stress is a leading cause of attrition among adult students. Many learners struggle to afford the costs associated with higher education, which can affect their academic success. Financial challenges can also limit access to necessary resources such as technology, study materials, and even basic needs like food and housing. This financial strain can create a stressful learning environment and force students to make difficult choices between education and other essential expenses.

Carrying children to school for adult learners who are also parents and managing their children's school schedules can be a major challenge. According to Ross-Gordon (2011), balancing parental responsibilities with academic commitments requires significant time and effort, often leading to stress and fatigue. The logistical challenges of coordinating children's school activities, transportation, and care can interfere with a parent's own study time and academic commitments. Providing on-campus childcare facilities and flexible class schedules can help alleviate some of these pressures and support adult learners in achieving a better balance between their parental duties and educational goals (Kasworm et al., 2010).

Work balancing work and study is one of the most significant challenges for adult learners. According to Wyatt (2011), many adult students are employed full-time or part-time, which can limit the time available for studying and attending classes. This dual responsibility often leads to exhaustion and decreased academic performance. Flexible work schedules and supportive employers are crucial for helping these learners succeed. Employers who offer flexibility in work hours and understanding of educational commitments can greatly enhance the ability of adult learners to manage both work and study effectively.

Adult learners face numerous challenges in adjusting to their studies, particularly in the areas of technology use, multitasking, budgeting, childcare, and work. Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach, including improved access to technology, financial support, childcare services, and flexible scheduling. By understanding and mitigating these barriers, educational institutions can better support adult learners in achieving their academic goals.

Difficulties Faced in Understanding the Lesson. Six junior high school informants from ALS share experiences as to what part of studies finds hard to adjust. The emerging themes are using technology, not being familiar with the lesson, not focus, difficulty in understanding English, conflicts in time, and none so far.

Using Technology can be both a tool and a hurdle in the learning process. Many adult learners struggle with using new technological tools, which can hinder their ability to access and engage with course materials. (Lai et al. 2015) emphasize the need for targeted support and training to help learners overcome these technological barriers. They argue that without proper guidance and resources, adult learners may face significant obstacles in navigating digital platforms and tools essential for modern education.

Adult learners who are not familiar with the lesson often encounter difficulties when they are not familiar with the lesson content, particularly if they have been away from formal education for an extended period. (Tinto 2012) notes that prior educational gaps can make it challenging for learners to engage fully with new material, necessitating additional support and resources. This lack of familiarity can lead to anxiety and a lack of confidence, further inhibiting their ability to succeed academically.

Cannot focus maintaining focus during lessons can be difficult for adult learners, especially when balancing multiple responsibilities. Junco et al. (2012) found that external distractions and multitasking can significantly reduce cognitive performance and hinder learning. They highlight that adult learners, who often juggle work, family, and study commitments, are particularly susceptible to these distractions, which can severely impact their ability to concentrate and absorb new information.

Difficulty in understanding English language barriers can significantly impact the ability of non-native English speakers to understand lessons. According to Crandall et al. (2004), limited proficiency in English can affect comprehension, participation, and academic performance. They advocate for the implementation of ESL (English as a Second Language) programs and additional language support services to help these learners overcome linguistic challenges and achieve academic success.

Conflict of time and time conflicts between educational commitments and other responsibilities can impede academic success. Kahu et al. (2013) highlight that time management is a critical skill for adult learners, and conflicts between work, family, and school schedules can be a significant barrier. These time conflicts can result in missed classes, incomplete assignments, and overall academic strain, making effective time management strategies essential for adult learners.

None so far have some learners reported any difficulties in understanding their lessons, often due to strong support systems, prior educational experience, or effective study habits. Tinto (2012) suggests that these learners benefit from intrinsic motivation and access to adequate resources, which can facilitate a smoother educational experience. These learners often exhibit high levels of self-discipline and resourcefulness, enabling them to navigate academic challenges more effectively.

Struggles in Going to School. Six senior high school informants from dysfunctional family share the same experiences as to how the challenges affected them and their studies. The emerging themes are school distance, time conflict, financial and home responsibilities. This is how the research informants describe their struggles in going to school.

School distance the physical distance to school can significantly impact students, particularly adult learners who may have additional responsibilities. According to Hagedorn et al. (2000), long commutes can reduce the time available for study and rest, leading to increased stress and decreased academic performance. Additionally, transportation costs can add a financial burden, making it more challenging for students to attend classes regularly. Strategies such as offering online courses or satellite campuses can help mitigate these challenges by providing more flexible learning options.

Time conflicts, as discussed in the previous theme that time conflicts between educational commitments and other responsibilities are a common struggle for adult learners. Kahu et al. (2013) highlight that managing time effectively is crucial for academic success. Many

adult learners juggle work, family, and study commitments, leading to scheduling conflicts that can hinder their ability to attend classes and complete assignments. Institutions can support these learners by offering flexible class schedules, evening or weekend courses, and asynchronous online learning opportunities.

Financial constraints are a significant barrier to education for many students. Tuition, textbooks, transportation, and other expenses can be prohibitive, especially for those supporting families. Goldrick-Rab et al. (2017) found that financial stress is prevalent among students and can lead to food insecurity and housing instability. This financial burden can detract from a learner's ability to focus on their studies and may result in higher dropout rates.

Home Responsibilities Balancing home responsibilities with academic commitments is particularly challenging for adult learners who may have caregiving duties for children or elderly family members. According to Ross-Gordon (2011), these responsibilities require significant time and energy, which can detract from study time and lead to increased stress and fatigue. Institutions can support these learners by offering on-campus childcare services, flexible scheduling, and resources for managing caregiving responsibilities.

Adult learners face numerous challenges in their educational journeys, particularly in balancing school with other life responsibilities. Distance to school, time conflicts, financial constraints, and home responsibilities are significant barriers that can impede their academic success. Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach from educational institutions, including the provision of flexible learning options, financial support, and resources for managing caregiving responsibilities. By understanding and mitigating these struggles, educational institutions can better support adult learners in achieving their academic goals.

Time Affecting in School. This structured theme summarizes the challenges encountered by six senior high school students as to how time affects studies in school. The emerging themes are nothing: the need to practice time management, the need to get up early, dividing time between school and work, and choosing between motherhood and being a student.

Need to get up early getting up early can provide students with additional time to dedicate to their studies, potentially enhancing their academic performance. Research by Vanderkam (2010) suggests that early risers often experience increased productivity and focus, allowing them to accomplish more tasks throughout the day. However, the effectiveness of this strategy may vary depending on individual preferences and circadian rhythms.

Dividing time between school and work and balancing school and work responsibilities can pose significant challenges for students. According to Ngo et al. (2020), students who work while attending school often experience higher levels of stress and lower academic performance compared to their non-working counterparts. Effective time management, flexible work arrangements, and clear communication with employers are essential for students navigating the demands of both school and work.

Choosing between motherhood and being a student for students who are also mothers, the decision to prioritize either their academic pursuits or their caregiving responsibilities can be particularly challenging. Research by Antonucci (2001) highlights the complexities of balancing motherhood with educational goals, noting that mothers often face societal pressures and expectations that can influence their decision-making process. Institutions can support student mothers by providing childcare services, flexible academic accommodations, and resources for navigating the challenges of parenthood while pursuing higher education.

Time management plays a crucial role in academic success, especially for students balancing multiple responsibilities. Effective time management strategies can help students optimize their study habits, increase productivity, and reduce stress. However, the challenges of time management vary depending on individual circumstances, such as work obligations, family responsibilities, and personal preferences.

Ways to overcome struggles in studies. Informants have shared how they overcame the struggles encountered in studies. Out of their responses, six themes were drawn out. These are collecting learning materials, moral support from husband, do internet research, motivate self not to surrender, prayer, and perseverance.

Collecting learning materials in the study of Soetan et al. (2010); they particularly stated that graphics, posters, cartoon sketches and, drawings, and graphs found in developed instructional materials help learners increase their level of understanding and could help them communicate facts and ideas clearly. It also helps learners to visualize the concepts learned and its relationship to others.

Moral support from husband wives and husbands in the study concurred that husbands should be emotionally and physically present to their wives, show consideration for her circumstances, and have a positive outlook, in line with findings by Kaye et al. (2014).

Do internet research Sylvia (2000) asserts that the use of the internet in education can support personalized learning and instruction by improving delivery speed, fostering the growth of writing and communication abilities, and boosting learning motivation and self-sufficiency. In addition, the use of a specialized information system and the Universal International Research System require access to the internet.

Motivate self not to surrender high motivation among students fosters a positive attitude on life as well as positive academic attainment and performance, claims Datu (2017). In order to use these things as an anchor or the primary reason for their hard work in the classroom and desire to fulfill their life's ambitions, students must discover what drives them.

Prayer according to Masters and Spielmans, Psychological Theory of Prayer (2007). This hypothesis proposes that people who are dealing with stress, uncertainty, or challenging circumstances might use prayer as a coping method. This idea holds that prayer can offer consolation, a sense of control, and a link to something bigger than oneself, which can have positive psychological effects, including lowered anxiety and boost resilience.

Grit becomes especially important for ALS learners, who frequently have different educational backgrounds and confront unique challenges. These students may face a variety of difficulties, including resource constraints, personal difficulties, and academic setbacks. ALS students who possess grit are able to persevere in the face of hardship, show resiliency, and put forth consistent effort to achieve their academic objectives.

Ways in Adapting Study Routines To Overcome Obstacles. Informants have shared how they adapt study routines to overcome obstacles. Out of their responses, five themes were drawn out. These are keeping up with technology, seeking help with family, doing research, making extra effort, and praying. This is how informants share their ways in adapting study routines.

Keeping up with technology young and adult learners already have access to wireless technology in many nations throughout the world, enabling them to learn in formal, informal, or neither setting at their own pace, at any time, or both (Lai et al., 2010).

Seek help with family, according to the study of Guanzon-Lapena and Jacob (2017), looked at the elements that lead to the success of ALS students in the Philippines. According to the study, ALS learners' success is mostly dependent on their families, the learning environment they are in, and the way they are taught.

Do research just like I the previous discussion according to Sylvia (2000) asserts that the use of the internet in education can support personalized learning and instruction by improving delivery speed, fostering the growth of writing and communication abilities, and boosting learning motivation and self-sufficiency. In addition, the use of a specialized information system and the Universal International Research System require access to the Internet.

Pray is the best weapon just like again in the previous discussion and it strong believed according to Pray Masters & Spielmans, Psychological Theory of Prayer (2007). This hypothesis proposes that people who are dealing with stress, uncertainty, or challenging circumstances might use prayer as a coping method. This idea holds that prayer can offer consolation, a sense of control, and a link to something bigger than oneself, which can have positive psychological effects including lowered anxiety and boosted resilience.

Support From Peers or Educators to Address Challenges. This structured theme summarizes how they seek support. The emerging themes are when using technology when it is hard to understand lessons, and when doing assignments. The research informants describe their motivation to continue learning or studying.

When using technology, technology is very rampant in fact most of the informants have common answers about using technology just like in the previous discussion, Sylvia (2000) asserts that the use of the internet in education can support personalized learning and instruction by improving delivery speed, fostering the growth of writing and communication abilities, and boosting learning motivation and self-sufficiency. In addition, the use of a specialized information system and the Universal International Research System require access to the internet.

When it is hard to understand the lesson, understanding and addressing learning challenges are critical to student success in educational contexts. Liao and Hsieh (2011) concentrated on internet-based learning, which can support students' education and help them get the skills necessary to become more engaged learners who can exchange knowledge with one another on online networks (Hofmann, 2002; Koper, 2009; Sloep & Berlanga, 2011).

Solutions Found When the Lesson Hard to Understand. Informants have shared how they found solutions when lessons were hard to understand. Out of their responses, three themes were drawn out. These are teachers who do internet research and help each other.

Ask teachers consulting teachers is a traditional yet effective approach for students to clarify doubts and gain deeper insights into lessons. Teachers possess subject matter expertise and can provide personalized guidance tailored to individual student needs. According to Hattie (2009), teacher-student interaction significantly impacts student learning outcomes, as teachers can offer immediate feedback and adjust their instructional methods to meet students' needs.

Do internet research with the advent of digital technology; internet research has become a valuable tool for students. The internet offers a vast repository of information that students can access to supplement their understanding of lesson content. A study by Tsai et al. (2010) highlighted that internet-based learning resources significantly enhance students' information literacy and problem-solving skills, thereby improving their academic performance.

The themes supported by the literature indicates that asking teachers, conducting internet research, and helping each other are effective strategies for enhancing student understanding of difficult lessons. Each method offers unique benefits that can complement each other to create a comprehensive approach to learning.

Message to Department of Education. This structured theme shows common feelings of six senior high school students towards to Department of Education. Out of their responses two themes were drawn out. These are grateful and a very big help. This is how all

informants describe what they say to the Department of Education.

Grateful Gratitude is a part of human personality. It is because gratitude is associated with well-being and happiness in life, mental health, and life satisfaction. Gratitude is also related to close social relationships and physical health (Wood et al., 2007). Gratitude as a personality has a positive outlook (Efers, 2016) and appreciates the values of kindness done by others (Emmons & Stern, 2013).

A very big help is already stated in the review-related literature that ALS provides a second chance at schooling to marginalized learners, who are able to find a better job and pursue further education. The program requires highly dedicated and multi-skilled teachers who have to deal with diverse types of learners. Nevertheless, reports from the study by Arzadon and Nato (2015) show that ALS has not produced significant results that address the needs of out-of-school youth and adults.

Lessons learned from The Experiences. Informants have shared the lessons they learned from the experiences. Out of their responses, eight themes were drawn out. These are being determined and working harder, never getting discouraged easily, pushing dreams beyond, never rushing life decisions, making hardship an inspiration, age and responsibilities, not a hindrance, never getting affected by any situation, and grabbing the opportunity to finish studies.

Being determined and work harder is a critical factor in achieving educational and personal goals. Duckworth et al. (2007) highlight the importance of grit—defined as perseverance and passion for long-term goals as a predictor of success. Their research shows that individuals with higher levels of grit are more likely to achieve their objectives despite obstacles.

Never get discouraged easily resilience is essential for overcoming setbacks and maintaining motivation. Masten (2014) describes resilience as "ordinary magic," emphasizing that it is a common trait that can be developed and strengthened. Resilient individuals are better equipped to handle adversity and persist in their efforts.

Pushing dreams beyond setting high aspirations and striving to achieve them is crucial for personal growth. Locke et al. (2002) argue that goal-setting theory underscores the significance of setting challenging goals, which enhances motivation and performance. High aspirations drive individuals to reach beyond their current capabilities.

Never rush life decisions. Taking the time to make informed and thoughtful decisions leads to better outcomes. Kahneman (2011), in "Thinking, Fast and Slow," explains the benefits of slow, deliberate decision-making processes. By avoiding hasty choices, individuals can weigh options more carefully and select the best action.

Making hardship an inspiration and transforming challenges into motivational forces can lead to personal growth. Tedeschi et al. (2004) introduce the concept of posttraumatic growth, which describes how individuals can develop new strengths and perspectives after experiencing significant adversity. Hardship can be a catalyst for positive change.

The lessons learned from personal experiences serve as powerful guides in the pursuit of educational and life goals. Determination, resilience, high aspirations, thoughtful decision-making, inspiration from hardship, the dismissal of age and responsibilities as barriers, maintaining focus, and seizing educational opportunities are all critical components for success. By understanding and applying these principles, individuals can navigate their challenges more effectively and work towards their aspirations with greater confidence and competence.

Views of Community to ALS Graduate. This structured theme summarizes the views of six senior high school students as to what they want the community to think of ALS graduates. Out of their responses, eight themes were drawn out. These are all students who have the same hardship, are viewed as regular students, are proud and respectful, think of ALS as part of DepEd, sacrifice, and determination to go to school. ALS gives hope; success is not a race and never discriminates against ALS graduates.

ALS gives hope. ALS programs offer hope and opportunities for marginalized or left behind by the formal education system. (UNESCO 2015) reports that alternative education systems play a critical role in providing educational access to underserved populations and promoting equity and social justice.

Success is not a race the notion that success is not a race but a personal journey helps reduce pressure and promotes a healthier approach to education. Seligman (2011) advocates for a focus on individual well-being and achievement rather than competition, fostering a more supportive and inclusive educational environment.

The community's views on ALS graduates significantly impact their acceptance and success. Recognizing that all students face similar hardships, treating ALS graduates as regular graduates, showing pride and respect, and considering ALS as a part of DepEd are essential steps toward fostering an inclusive and supportive environment. ALS programs provide hope and opportunities, and the sacrifices made by ALS students demonstrate their determination and resilience.

Conclusions

Based on the data I have gathered, different experiences of students from ALS learners were explored and unfolded. They have shared their struggles, inspirations, coping mechanism, insights, and motivation in life.

As a researcher, I was able to explore the untold stories and experiences of the students from ALS learners. I was moved as I got to see

the pain and hopes in their eyes as they shared their lived experiences. Coping with such domestic responsibility is not that easy. There are many adversities as they face the demands of life. Their longing for acceptance in the community affects their behavior and even their perception of life. This is something that teachers and policymakers must take into account.

Education is believed to be the most powerful weapon a person may have. However, there are really individuals who struggle to have access to education due to many reasons. Therefore, the Department of Education (DepEd) established the Alternative Learning System (ALS) as a parallel educational pathway for students who did not complete their basic education through the traditional school system. However, the problems of ALS students are still undoable. One of the problems a student faced before entering ALS was the lack of opportunities because they did not graduate secondary. The participant also mentioned being afraid to stand in front of other people. Another problem faced by ALS students is a lack of support from the community or the people around them. Another factor to take note of is the type of family where the student came from.

I believe that this study would enable the education and opening of the minds of the students, family, teachers, community, and other people around on their views on individuals from ALS, and understanding, acceptance, and sympathy would take place. By understanding the diverse needs of learners and providing appropriate support and resources, educational institutions can help students overcome time-related challenges and achieve their academic goals.

The following implications are considered for future researchers:

First, the study suggests further research be conducted to substantiate these responses using a greater number of participants. The greater the number of participants, the more life stories will be explored and unfolded.

Second, as a researcher, I suggest to include other schools as part of your research locale. This will allow for the investigation and exploration of more stories about the phenomenon.

Third, the study conducted in UNHS-Mt. Diwata Annex, further research could be done to explore the same phenomenon in another public school that have ALS learners.

Lastly, another research could be conducted to discover how teachers facilitate and monitor students from ALS.

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